

PORO-VASCULAR COMPOSITES WITH SURFACE ROUGHNESS CONTROL

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ABSTRACT

The Naval Research Laboratory (NRL) has been developing multifunctional “poro-vascular composites” (PVCs) with the capability for structure and active-addressable surface roughness control functionalities. PVCs are polymeric laminates with an ionic liquid (IL) constituent contained in an internal vascular network that connects with mm-scale pores on the surface. Control of the IL meniscus shape and height at the pore exits will enable a range of surface morphologies (domed-to-smooth-to-dimpled) that alter the surface roughness. Meniscus shape and height will be controlled using Electrowetting-on-Dielectric (EWOD) and pumping. PVCs are being explored for use as skin materials for boundary-layer flow control on airfoils (lift, drag, laminar-turbulent transition) and/or active thermal convection control. In this paper, we report initial efforts at synthesis of active, small-scale PVC arrays and explore the capabilities and limitations of three different EWOD control mechanisms, including control at the pore, inside a reservoir with controlled gas pressure, and inside a microchannel array. We identify several challenges, both intrinsic (overcome through system design) and extrinsic (overcome through process control and/or design). The results show that the most promising approach for achieving robust control of pore liquid shapes is to control a single meniscus curvature (i.e., pressure) at a location remote from the pores using EWOD together with displacement-pumping of the working liquid.

1 INTRODUCTION

NRL has been developing multifunctional “poro-vascular” composites (PVCs) with both structure and surface roughness control functionality [1,2]. PVCs are thin polymer laminates with an internal vascular channel network connected to sub mm-scale pore arrays on the surface. An ionic liquid (IL) constituent phase is contained within the pore-channel network, and control of the IL height and meniscus shape at the pore exits (Figure 1) enables active-addressable control of surface roughness with domed-smooth-dimpled IL morphologies. Volume-displacement pumping in the channels and contact angle control via electrode-wetting-on-dielectric are being employed to achieve IL height and meniscus shape control in multi-pore arrays.

Figure 1: Cross-section schematic (not to scale) illustrating a notional poro-vascular skin with different roughness states.

Prototype PVC “devices” were made from conductive and non-conductive polyimide and polyetherimide films. They were fabricated using laser micro-machining of individual lamina to create the channels and pores and then bonded together using an acrylic adhesive. Initial design concepts integrated EWOD at each pore for control of the IL menisci. This required a

conductive electrode on the pore-laminate surface extending a small distance into the pore (see Figure 4). All electrode surfaces had to be electrically insulated from the liquid with a thin dielectric + hydrophobic layer. Prior work [1,2] identified several challenges associated with liquid control in PVCs:

- EWOD for contact angle control of ILs on (non-standard) polyimide surfaces;
- Filling the vascular channels (void-free) and preventing liquid siphoning from the pores; and
- Coating the EWOD conductor in pore-channel geometries with the required thin, pin-hole free dielectric and hydrophobic layers.

Given the challenges of implementing EWOD control in PVC-like geometries, it might be questioned whether EWOD is actually necessary for liquid shape control in the pores. Pumping alone may be able to create the desired dome-to-dimple transition with an appropriate pore exit geometry (e.g., re-entrant edges at the pore exit). However, there are significant advantages to a combined approach. Foremost is that EWOD provides control of liquid pressure through the meniscus curvature. Because of this, EWOD may be much more robust in a flexible skin system where the vascular network and pore volumes may change (be squeezed) as the PVC laminate is flexed. EWOD also provides a potential feedback-loop via capacitance [3], and a more rapid rate of change in contact angle.

Figure 2a shows a flat substrate EWOD test specimen, and Figure 2b shows the typical contact angle behaviour with applied potential ($+V$ shown; symmetric about contact angle axis for $-V$). The EWOD process involves a balance between charge repulsion in the IL at the solid interface and IL surface tension. The Lippmann-Young equation relates contact angle, θ , to the applied potential, V :

$$\cos\theta = \cos\theta_0 + \frac{\epsilon_0\epsilon}{2t\gamma}V^2 \quad (1)$$

In Eq. (1), θ_0 is the contact angle at zero voltage, ϵ_0 the permittivity of free space, ϵ the dielectric constant for the dielectric + hydrophobic coating, γ the interfacial tension of the liquid-phase, and t the coating thickness. Contact angle decreases with $\pm V$ (Figure 2b; green dashed line), but it will eventually saturate at some voltage level. Several mechanisms have been proposed for saturation including: dielectric breakdown and charge trapping [4,5]; air ionization at the triple-line [6]; and finite conductivity of the liquid [7]. From a design perspective, maximal change in contact angle with applied V is desired. Eq. (1) shows that this requires maximizing the dielectric constant ϵ and minimizing the thickness t . Interfacial tension, γ , affects both θ_0 and the EWOD voltage factor.

We have characterized EWOD on flat silicon and various polyimide substrates, all of which had a ~ 5 μm layer of Parylene-C applied followed by a 100-200 nm thick spin-coated layer of Teflon AF1600. The results shown in Figure 2c are averages for each liquid over all tested substrates, which have no discernible effect on EWOD. The effect of using different liquids (two different ILs and 0.1 M NaCl) is a change in zero-potential contact angle, but all three liquids show the same saturation angle. It also shows that liquids with larger γ ($\gamma_{aq} > \gamma_{IL2} > \gamma_{IL4}$) exhibit larger changes in contact angle ($\theta_0 - \theta_{sat}$) before saturation. Other results show a decrease in hysteresis (advancing minus receding contact angle) with increasing potential, and a history-dependent stick-slip (ratcheting) of the advancing contact angle.

Other research on EWOD has examined the effect of an AC voltage instead of DC (typically 0-10 kHz) as well as differences between positive and negative DC voltage EWOD. The Lippmann-Young equation predicts no difference between DC and AC EWOD nor for positive vs negative EWOD [8]. However, AC EWOD has been shown to be more effective at actuating contact line movement on rough surfaces. The AC voltage may produce local microscopic vibrations of the contact line, which helps to overcome surface heterogeneities that typically pin the contact line [9,10]. Similarly, small differences have been observed in positive vs. negative EWOD, particularly the saturation level. These may be related to ion size or to a slight affinity between negative ions and Teflon surfaces [11].

Figure 2: (a) flat substrate EWOD experiment; (b) typical EWOD behavior; (c) experimental EWOD results for three liquids on Kapton and Silicon substrates with Parylene-C and Teflon AF coatings. Error bars are the 75% confidence limits.

Other prior results related to the selection of materials for making PVCs, laser micro-machining of pores, arrays, and vascular channels, channel-filling experiments, mechanical testing of PVC candidate materials and some actual PVC prototype laminates, and computation and wind-tunnel experimentation to examine the effects of PVC-scale dome morphologies on boundary-layer drag and tripping on a low-Reynold's number airfoil can be found in Thomas et al. [1,2].

This paper will report on recent progress with making and testing several PVC prototype designs for their liquid control performance. The prototype designs, materials, and fabrication methods will be described first. A brief description will be given of some methods for applying hydrophobic coatings in pore geometries including SEM characterization. Experimental results will be reported on meniscus and height control of a liquid in a nine-pore array using three different EWOD control strategies. The implications for future work and PVC design are then discussed as a conclusion to the paper.

2 METHODS

Three different prototype designs were fabricated. The first employed the concept of EWOD control at the pore exits. It consisted of a top pore layer of Kapton RS with thin dielectric and hydrophobic coatings, a middle “vascular-reservoir” layer made of 1 mm thick Ultem (polyetherimide), and a 1 mm thick base layer of Ultem. The edges of the reservoir extended beyond the pore-array envelope with nominal dimensions of 7-8 mm square by 1-2 mm deep. The top pore layer (15 mm square) was made with 200RS100 Kapton (25 μm conductive carbon-polyimide layer bonded to 25 μm thick polyimide layer). Nine 1 mm diameter pores with 1 mm edge-edge spacing were laser micro-machined. The conductive side was vapor-coated with 6.7 μm of Parylene-C dielectric and then spin-coated with Teflon 1600AF. Teflon AF was dissolved in Fluorinert FC-72 (1% by weight) and then dispensed on the pore-layer that was rotating at 6000 rpm. It was allowed to rotate for an additional 2 minutes followed by baking at 70°C for 2-3 hours. When assembled, the conductive side of the Kapton RS was oriented outwards (Figure 3a).

Figure 3: (a) open-reservoir multi-pore design (Prototype #1); (b) prototype showing the different layers; (c) assembled prototype for liquid morphology control experiments.

Figure 4: Pore cross-section showing the dielectric and hydrophobic coatings that must extend down into the pore.

Preliminary to the fabrication of the first prototype, some experiments were performed to determine viable techniques for applying the Teflon AF coating over the Parylene-C coated pore-layer. Parylene is a conformal, vapor-deposited coating, and it polymerizes in-situ. It readily coats the conductive edges of the Kapton RS inside the pore walls (see Figure 4). Various techniques were tried to achieve a uniform coating of Teflon AF extending down into the 1 mm diameter pores. The first method consisted of dipping a Si substrate sample with a 1 mm diameter laser micro-machined pore into different concentrations of Teflon AF solutions. Following removal, they were baked at 70 °C for 2 hours and then cleaved across the pore diameter to reveal the cross-section. As seen in Figure 5, the Teflon coatings on the pore walls were relatively thick, and the

thickness did not change much with Teflon AF concentration.

Figure 5: Si-pore immersion samples showing the Teflon AF coating within the pore. The white scale-bars in the photos represent 10 μm on the top row and 1 μm on the bottom row.

The second method consisted of spin-coating Teflon AF onto a Si-pore sample. The Si-pore samples were prepared the same way as before, and they were elevated on the spin-coater to allow solution to exit freely at the bottom of the pore. Figure 6 shows that the resulting Teflon AF layer is quite thin. Spin-coating resulted in a thinner, more uniform coating within the pore compared with dip-coating.

Extending the spin-coating process from a single pore to a multi-pore array necessitated a further refinement. Figure 7 shows two Parylene coated Kapton RS test samples that were coated with a 1% Teflon AF solution using dispense-spin (a) or dispense-while-spinning (b) approaches. While a dispense-spin is the traditional method used for spin coating, the dispense-while-spinning method clearly achieved a better quality Teflon AF coating. The multi-color reflections (light refraction) from the surface of (b) indicate the presence of a non-uniform Teflon AF layer thickness.

Figure 6: Si-pore spin-coat samples showing the Teflon AF coating inside the pore. The white scale-bars in the photos represent 10 μm on the top row and left bottom and 1 μm on the right bottom.

Figure 7: (a) static dispensing of 1% Teflon AF solution on Parylene coated Kapton RS followed by spinning at 6000 rpm; (b) dynamic dispensing of 1% Teflon AF solution while spinning at 6000 rpm. The pores are all 1.0 mm in diameter.

Figure 8: modified open-reservoir design (Prototype #2). Control of the air-liquid meniscus curvature in the reservoir is used to control the liquid curvature at the pore exits. The three camera views used in the experiments are shown, and note that the polyetherimide is semi-transparent.

The second PVC prototype involved connecting a second reservoir in series with the first prototype (Figure 8). The second reservoir was capped with an electroded Kapton RS layer (no pores), with the conductive layer facing inwards. A gas port connected to a large syringe pump enabled control of the pressure acting in the reservoir. Fluid pressure was controlled in the second reservoir section via the

Young-Laplace relation through curvature control of the air-liquid meniscus in the reservoir using EWOD and gas back-pressure. Different camera views were used in the experiments and are indicated in Figure 8 for understanding the photograph views shown below in the Results section.

Figure 9: (a) microchannel-reservoir design (Prototype #3); (b) assembled prototype, view from the bottom-up; (c) microchannels cross-section; (d) top view of the microchannels.

The third prototype incorporated a row of tapering microchannels in-series with the vascular reservoir, capped by a coated Kapton RS pore-array layer, but with electrode side down towards the reservoir (Figure 9). The microchannels were designed to enable amplification of range of liquid menisci shapes possible in the surface pores, from domed-to-flat-to-dimpled. Amplification is possible when the liquid-solid contact angles in the microchannels lead to larger curvatures than can be achieved in a larger pore with the same contact angle [12]. The tapered design for the microchannels was employed to facilitate liquid filling from the reservoir. It also provided position-dependent menisci curvatures through movement of the liquid in the channel with displacement pumping, and hence, adjustable liquid pressure control for surface pore morphology amplification.

All of the prototypes were assemblies of individual layers that were laser micro-machined separately before consolidation bonding. The ULTEM polyetherimide layers were machined using a 355 nm Nd:YVO₄ (JDSU Q301) laser with pulses that were modulated and focused by a hi-speed galvo-mirror scanhead (Scanlab hurrySCAN 10). ULTEM readily absorbs UV, so laser pulses with energies > 800 μJ ($\sim 15 \mu\text{m}$ diameter spot size) machined through the 1 mm sections in < 1 minute. Lower laser pulse energies (0.6 μJ) were used for machining the pore-arrays through the thinner RS Kapton layers, which also avoided the possibility of thermal damage. A pin-guided stacking-alignment fixture was used for registering the various layers during assembly and interlayer bonding (see Figure 3b). Double-sided acrylic tape (3M type 467MP), 50.8 μm thick, machined to the same planar dimensions as the reservoir layer, was used for interlayer bonding. The Luer needle for liquid insertion was bonded to a slot cut in the reservoir layer and epoxied before the top RS Kapton piece was attached. The entire assembly was then clamped and baked at 100°C for ~ 30 minutes; the bake temperature was limited by the maximum permissible temperature for the Parylene C. After baking, the pins were pushed out and the PVC prototype removed.

Unless otherwise noted, PVC reservoirs were connected by flexible tubing to a syringe pump (KDS310) filled with 50:50 solution of glycerol and 0.1 M NaCl. Electrical contact with the Kapton RS electrodes required locally scraping through the Teflon/Parylene coatings. Prior to EWOD testing, each prototype was screened for current leakage with a fully filled reservoir and pores (pass if < few nA current at 200 V). The EWOD testing started by filling the reservoir at a 2-5 $\mu\text{l}/\text{min}$ flow rate until a convex (domed) meniscus profile was formed in the pores. EWOD responses were then measured under applied AC or DC voltages with the Kapton RS electrically grounded. Cameras viewing the top, side, and (when needed) bottom of the pore array (Figure 8) recorded the response. Unless otherwise noted, the cameras (Prosilica GC750 and GC1600H), power supply (Agilent 6612C with a TREK 2050

amplifier), and voltage/current meter (National Instruments PXI-4071) were controlled by LabView. For each test, the images, applied EWOD voltage, current through the dielectric layer, and relevant time stamps were logged at a rate of ~1-4 Hz. A clear view of the liquid menisci below the Kapton RS surface was not possible, which prevented measurement of the concave (dimpled) menisci angles. Convex contact angles were determined by post-processing the side-on image using either FTA32 [13] or FIJI [14] software.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Prototype #1: EWOD at the pore exit-surface

EWOD behavior of Prototype #1 is shown in Figure 10. A very dramatic change in pore menisci states was observed when the EWOD voltage was applied. One pore would overflow while all the other pore menisci dropped to a nearly flat configuration. This effect was irreversible. That is, when the voltage was turned off, the contact angle exhibited by the overflowed drop did return (increase) to its equilibrium (0 V) value, but it did so while remaining extended on the PVC surface beyond the pore exit boundary. Liquid did not flow back into the reservoir and refill the other pores. Repeated EWOD voltage cycling simply moved between the two states with relatively minor accompanying changes in meniscus shape change at the other pores.

In contrast to our previous work, which examined EWOD combined with pumping in a glass capillary [2], the experiments here maintained constant fluid volume while changing the applied EWOD voltage (i.e., no pumping adjustments). Liquid was pumped into the reservoir until domed menisci formed in the pores, then the pumping was stopped and DC EWOD voltages applied. As the voltage was applied, the contact angles at the pore exits were driven to decrease, but they were prevented from doing so by the constant volume constraint. A reduction in contact angle corresponds to a transformation from domed-to-flat-to-dimpled, which requires accommodation of the “domed” parts of the pore liquid volumes. Upon application of the EWOD voltage, the pore with either the largest diameter or the least pinning (smoothest pore-surface transition) allowed the meniscus to begin to overflow onto the surface. The pores were all fluidically connected and were hence subject to the same liquid pressure, which collectively equalized their menisci curvatures. Once any one pore began to overflow, its curvature (pressure) reduced, and all the other pores followed with identical reductions in their curvatures producing a more flat-dimpled state.

Figure 10: (a)-(e) Pore menisci states in Prototype #1 with a series of applied DC EWOD voltages from 0 to +210 to 0 to -210 and then back to 0 V. The pores are all 1.0 mm in diameter.

3.2 Prototype #2: EWOD in the reservoir

The effect of EWOD inside an internal reservoir rather than at the pore exits was investigated using Prototype #2. To test this concept, a “EWOD-actuation reservoir” was connected to Prototype #1 as shown in Figure 8. The new reservoir had no pores, and the Kapton RS electrode was oriented to the interior rather than outwards. A 10 mL syringe was connected to vent the reservoir and apply controlled backpressures. It was sufficiently large in volume to prevent significant changes in air backpressure with changes in (reservoir) meniscus position. After filling the system so that the meniscus in the EWOD reservoir was visible (~half-way across in the bottom view), pressure was applied by the syringe until the liquid bulged out of the pores. Voltage was then applied for EWOD-actuation in the reservoir. The photographs in Figure 11 show three camera views for one-cycle of EWOD-actuation. The pore array menisci are shown for the different EWOD voltages (angled-view) along with the contact angles (side-

view) and the reservoir meniscus (bottom view). Changes in pore contact angle with applied AC voltage were small $\sim 15\text{-}20^\circ$, but the changes were largely reversible.

3.3 Prototype #3: EWOD in reservoir microchannels

Prototype #3 (Figure 9) employed a set of 8 microchannels at one end of an elongated EWOD reservoir similar to Prototype #1. Each microchannel was 2.27 mm long and 550 μm deep and had a 538 μm wide entrance that tapered to 330 μm width at the air-side exits. The Kapton RS was oriented with the electrode side toward the reservoir interior. The system was filled up to the microchannel entrances. At that point, because the pore diameter was larger than the microchannel cross-section, liquid preferentially bulged out of the pores instead of filling the microchannels.

Figure 11: EWOD in Prototype #2. a) shows a 79° contact angle, b) 57° , and c) 73° . The photos on the left shows a bottom view of the meniscus (dark) in the reservoir ($\sim 7 \times 7 \text{ mm}$), the middle photos show an angled view of the pore menisci, and the right shows meniscus side views (all 1 mm diameter).

Figure 12: EWOD in Prototype #3. a) 63° contact angle, b) 30° , and c) 37° . The photos on the left show an angled view of the array menisci, and the right meniscus side views (all 1 mm diameter).

The photographs in Figure 12 show the pore menisci (angle-view) for a 0-500-0 VDC EWOD cycle; to the right are side-on views of a pore meniscus contact angle. The total change in angle was larger (~30°), but it was not reversible. In Figure 12c, the contact angle returned to 37° not the original 63° when voltage was set back to zero. A view from the bottom (not shown) showed liquid pinning occurring in the microchannels, which would explain the observed contact angle hysteresis.

4 DISCUSSION

The science of multifunctional materials encompasses both “materials” (properties) and “systems-level” (functions) considerations. What we report here are the first experimental steps in property-system testing of PVCs with integrated multi-pore arrays, EWOD electroding, liquid pumping, and gas pressure control. The focus was on design mechanisms for liquid menisci control (domed-to-dimpled) implemented in three prototypes. Below, we will examine and discuss the ‘pros and cons’ of each design from both performance (function) and manufacturability (properties).

The most obvious result and conclusion is that the largest approximate contact angle change with applied voltage was a modest ~33°, and a dimpled state was never achieved. This reflects the known limitations of only using the EWOD-actuation mechanism to affect changes in the contact angle. Volume (displacement) pumping and possibly gas back-pressure control are also needed in conjunction with EWOD to achieve the largest range of liquid menisci shape control in a pore array.

The biggest challenge associated with manufacturability of Prototype #1 (EWOD at the pore exits on the exterior surface) was that of achieving a (uniform) dielectric coating over all electrode surfaces including those extending into each pore. The vapor-deposited Parylene-C was effective in coating all exposed electrode surfaces, and further optimization of the Teflon AF spin-coating is possible [15]. However, we found that the system behavior was sensitive to coating, with any pinholes leading to short-circuiting (current flow) when the voltage was applied. The observed EWOD behavior for Prototype #1 was more complex. No change in menisci shapes were observed with applied voltage until one of the pores overflowed. The overflow and subsequent siphoning of liquid out of all the other pores occurred quickly once started. This is due to the common pressure of the contiguous liquid, which enforces identical menisci curvatures regardless of variations in pore exit geometry. In circular pores, the menisci are spherical caps, so larger pore diameters have larger “liquid domes.” This spreads the meniscus further out from the edge of the pore (relative to all the others), so that when a small-enough contact angle is reached (via EWOD), the liquid from this larger diameter pore will start spreading-out. As it spreads on the surface, the curvature reduces, and this forces the liquid menisci curvatures in all the other pores to reduce through liquid siphoning into the larger drop and subsequent flattening. The common liquid pressure provides a remarkably robust mechanism for liquid control, but it can also present challenges to the PVC design. If any single pore in a connected system starts overflowing, then all the others pores will immediately begin losing liquid to the overflowing pore. As the number of connected pores increases, the volume of liquid that can be lost increases, and as was observed, the overflow process is irreversible. One final point is that Prototype #1 is intrinsically limited to a domed-to-flat transition using only EWOD control. EWOD control of a liquid spreading across a surface will always be convex (positive pressure), which means that all connected menisci, regardless of size or pore shape, must also be convex.

Prototype #2 moved EWOD control to the reservoir’s meniscus curvature, which controlled the pore menisci through the balance of liquid pressure at the two liquid-gas interfaces:

$$\frac{2\gamma \cos \theta_p}{a} = \frac{\gamma \cos \theta_r}{a_H} \quad (2)$$

where γ is the liquid interfacial tension, θ the contact angle in the pore and reservoir (indicated by p and r subscripts, respectively), a is the pore radius and a_H is the hydraulic radius (area/circumference) for the reservoir. Since $a_H \sim 3a$ in the Prototype #2 design, the changes in θ_p with changes in θ_r are

attenuated by a factor of 6-7 at $\theta = 90^\circ$. For example, $\pm 10^\circ$ changes in θ_r produces approximately $\pm 1.5^\circ$ change in θ_p . This limitation is exhibited in Figure 11. Large meniscus motions in the reservoir produced small changes at the pore exit. This also explains why gas backpressure in the reservoir was required to bulge the liquid in the pores. Assuming similar contact angles in the reservoir and pore exits, only a few degrees of curvature can be achieved at the pore without adding a backpressure term on the right hand side of Eq. (2). However, the need for backpressure control introduces significant PVC design challenges. The first relates to making the reservoir chamber gas-tight. Air-leaks in our prototype devices caused many test failures. Second, the backpressure must either be actively controlled, or the volume of pressure-controlled air in the reservoir must be very large relative to the reservoir liquid volume changes by EWOD and pumping. For example, the transition of nine pores, each 1 mm in diameter, from fully domed to fully dimpled involves a change in liquid volume on the order of 5 μL . If this volume change is to be accommodated by the reservoir, with gas pressure changes less than 1%, then a gas volume reservoir 100x larger must be used (500 μL)!

Prototype #3 avoided the two complications associated with Prototype #2 by employing EWOD in the microchannel array, which had a smaller a_H than the pore diameter, a_p . In this case, gas backpressure was not required to achieve large changes in θ_p because EWOD control in the microchannels amplified pore curvature changes [12]. The use of eight microchannels in parallel were an attempt to accommodate pore volume changes in going from domed-to-dimpled. Unfortunately, the contact angle changes within the pores did not behave as predicted, with limited shape change and large irreversibility. We believe there are two reasons for this disparity. First, the microchannels were electroded on only one surface, which reduced the EWOD effect to essentially one-quarter of what might be possible. This can be resolved. The more significant issue was hysteresis by contact line pinning on the microchannel walls. This resisted meniscus advancement during EWOD induced wetting and resisted meniscus retreat upon voltage removal. The result was reduced change in contact angle by EWOD, and the changes that did occur were irreversible (large hysteresis).

4.1 Future Designs: EWOD-plus-Pumping

In designs like Prototype #3, pumping is required during EWOD-actuation to maintain a stable meniscus location with the microchannel(s) as liquid volume changes occur in the pores during transition to and from dome-to-dimple states. This would avoid potential wall pinning, which is nearly inevitable with small, machined microchannels where large meniscus movements occur during actuation. EWOD control of contact angle in a microchannel with a diameter smaller than that of the pores in the array will provide a useful range of menisci curvatures in the array pores (fully domed to fully dimpled) if the liquid meniscus in the microchannel can be kept “centered.” This approach to liquid morphology control can simplify PVC fabrication by allowing the use of a smooth non-polymeric material for the EWOD-microchannel instead of trying to machine precision microchannels in the base polyimide material. This PVC design appears promising and is being pursued in current research.

EWOD should not be employed for domed state control in designs like Prototype #1 since it is likely to lead to irreversible pore-spillage. Geometric features that promote pinning at the pore exit (e.g., corner-edge) and the low surface energy coating (Teflon AF) are sufficient to assure a fully domed shape via pumping without liquid spreading. EWOD voltages should only be applied at low liquid height states to avoid potential overflow conditions. EWOD creates a meniscus pinning force at the pore exit edge that enables a “deeper” dimpling state by liquid withdrawal by pumping.

In Prototype #1 designs, each pore must be appropriately electroded and coated with dielectric and hydrophobic layers for EWOD manipulation. The pore diameters and their wall surfaces must also be very uniform to avoid potential overflow instabilities. These designs are not expected to be as robust as Prototype #3 designs, because the electroded surface is on the exterior, exposed, and susceptible to scratches that can “short” the dielectric. By contrast, Prototype #3 designs have the active EWOD section of the device occurring in an interior microchannel, which would be well protected from potential mechanical damage.

5 CONCLUSIONS

We report initial experimental work on surface morphology control in multi-pore array PVC composites. For this study, the effect of three different EWOD actuation methods were examined: at the pore exits, inside of a “vented” reservoir, and within in an array of internal microchannels. The results provide useful understanding of both design and processing effects (e.g., channel wall roughness, dielectric and hydrophobic coatings at pore exits) on final shape control. Together, they demonstrate that a more robust method for liquid menisci control in multi-pore arrays would be EWOD in a “short” single-microchannel combined with volumetric pumping and gas back-pressure control. This design advancement is being prototyped and modeled to assess control capabilities, precision, and robustness for multifunctional PVC laminates.

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